

THIOKETONIC ESTERS. PART X.

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Cyclic β -thioketonic esters have been synthesised and investigated. The mechanism of the reaction of an unsymmetrical triad system with the aldehydes has been established. They have been utilised in the synthesis of hydrothionaphthenes.

The prototropic system present in chain β -thioketonic esters is in principle very much like that present in their oxygen analogues, excepting that the resonance isomer, which is predominating in the former, is otherwise in the case of the latter as a result of which there is a profound tendency of the former to give rise to *S*-ethers, and the latter *C*-ethers during substitution at the reactive centres (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 75 *et seq*).

Again, there is also a great tendency of "C-C-S" system to release anions in presence of electrophilic reagents and naturally so due to pronounced "T" effect, as the peripheral electrons of sulphur are much farther away from the nuclear effect than those of oxygen. This dual nature of a prototropic system could not be observed in system hitherto studied as the members concerned were always simplest members of the groups of periodic table. This great tendency in the case of thioketonic esters to liberate anions (SH^-) always gave difficulty in isolating the intermediate compound (I) which invariably decomposed in the presence of a condensing agent giving rise to thioaldehydes (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 18, 129).

[R and X = alkyl or aryl; X' = CO₂Et].

Due to reasons unknown at present, cyclic thioketonic esters which have been synthesised by the orthodox method (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 71) have been found less susceptible to reagents that help releasing anions from such systems. The alkylated products do not liberate mercaptans even on boiling with acids. They react with aldehydes in the thiol-phase as anticipated giving rise to hydroxy sulphide (II), which soon after

the liberation, lactonises to (III). These lactones are very stable compounds and unlike chain-thioketonic esters cannot furnish the thioaldehydes (Ia). These are new heterocyclic compounds and have been named "metathioxines."

It is interesting to note that somewhat different route is chosen by β -thiocyclopentanone carboxylic ester in the reaction. The hydroxy compound, previously described, instead of undergoing internal lactonisation reacts with another molecule of the ester in thiol-phase to give rise to a sulphide (IVa).

This is in agreement with what has been forestalled that the thiolised ester primarily adds to the carbonyl group giving rise to hydroxy sulphide.

α -Halogenated fatty esters have been condensed with the keto esters. The resulting products have been cyclised to give rise to thiophene bodies (VIII). Thiocyclohexanone carboxylic ester under this condition furnishes hexahydrothionaphthene (Va). Thio-thiol has been estimated by the iodometric method (Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1938, 15, 205).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Thio-ester.—The cyclic keto-ester was dissolved in ethyl alcohol (10 g. in 40 c.c.), saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0°, and hydrogen sulphide was passed (24 hours) through the solution standing over ice; the oil that separated was extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was washed with dilute sodium carbonate, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The benzene was removed, and the residual oil distilled under reduced pressure. The following compounds were thus prepared: *ethyl thiocyclopentan-1-one-2-carboxylate*, b. p. 110°/5.5 mm. (Found: C, 56.0; H, 7.3; S, 18.2. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9; S, 18.6 per cent). *Ethyl thiocyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate*, b. p. 112°/6 mm. (Found: C, 57.9; H, 7.36. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 58.07; H, 7.52 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Thio-esters.—When the above thio-esters (5-10 g.) were refluxed (4-6 hours) with 10% barium hydroxide (100 c.c.), only a small amount of the corresponding thio-acids was isolated. The yield was, however, considerably increased by the following process.

The thio-ester (2-2.5 g.) was taken in alcoholic sodium hydroxide (25 c.c. of 33%), and the mixture immediately heated on a water-bath (20 minutes). It was then quickly cooled over ice, the mixture acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold, rapidly filtered, and dried at 60° cautiously under suction. The crude acid was crystallised from a mixture of dry ether and petroleum ether (b.p. 80°-90°) giving glistening flakes (yield 60%). Following acids were isolated:—*Thiocyclopentan-1-one-2-carboxylic acid*, m.p. 122° (decomp.). (Found: S, 21.9. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 22.2 per cent). *Thiocyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylic acid*, m.p. 115° (decomp.). (Found: C, 52.9; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 53.2; H, 6.3 per cent).

Preparation of Alkyl and other Derivatives.—The thio-ester in sodium-dried benzene was slowly added to emulsified sodium, suspended in dry benzene at 0°. When the reaction had abated, the mixture was left (8 hours) at the room temperature (25°). Alkyl halides were then added and the mixture refluxed (6 hours). The product was cooled and treated with excess of water containing a few c.c. of hydrochloric acid and the benzene layer was collected and dried. The benzene was removed and the residual oil distilled. Following compounds were prepared :

Ethyl 1-ethylmercaptocyclopentene-2-carboxylate (VI, R=R'=Et), b.p. 115°/6 mm., from ethyl thiocyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (9 g.), ethyl iodide (32 g.), and emulsified sodium (1 g.). (Found : S, 15.6. C₁₀H₁₈O₂S requires S, 16.0 per cent). *Ethyl 1-methylcarbethoxymercaptocyclopentene-2-carboxylate*, (VI, R=Et; R'=CH₂CO₂Et), b.p. 170°/3 mm., from thiocyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (10 g.), ethyl monochloroacetate (19 g.) and emulsified sodium (1.5 g.). (Found : S, 12.7. C₁₂H₁₈O₄S requires S, 12.4 per cent). *Ethyl 1-ethylmercaptocyclohexene-2-carboxylate*, (VII, R=R'=Et), b.p. 125°/3 mm., from ethyl thiocyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (11 g.), ethyl iodide (23 g.) and molecular sodium (1.8 g.) (Found : C, 61.4; H, 8.56. C₁₁H₁₈O₂S requires C, 61.6; H, 8.4 per cent). *Ethyl 1-acetylmercaptocyclohexene-2-carboxylate*, (VII, R=Et; R'=CO^oMe), b.p. 132°/5 mm., from thiocyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (10 g.), acetylchloride (5 g.) and molecular sodium (1.1 g.). (Found : C, 57.8; H, 7.1; S, 13.5. C₁₁H₁₈O₃S requires C, 57.9; H, 7.0; S, 14.0 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the above Alkyl Derivatives.—The thio-esters (VI & VII) were dissolved in alcoholic sodium hydroxide (10 c.c.) in the cold and kept at room temperature for 8-10 hours. The mixture was cooled in ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold. The solid which separated was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate and liberated by dilute mineral acid, and crystallised from acetic acid (charcoal). The following compounds were obtained :

1-Ethylmercaptocyclopentene-2-carboxylic acid, (VI, R=H; R'=Et), m.p. 177°, from thio-ether (VI, R=R'=Et, 5 g.) and sodium hydroxide (1.4 g.). (Found : C, 55.6; H, 6.9; S, 18.4. C₈H₁₂O₂S requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9; S, 18.6 per cent). *1-Ethylmercaptocyclohexene-2-carboxylic acid*, (VII, R=H; R'=Et), m.p. 146° from thio-ether (VIII, R=R'=Et, 5 g.) and sodium hydroxide (2 g.). (Found : C, 57.9; H, 7.4. C₉H₁₄O₂S requires C, 58.0; H, 7.5 per cent).

The thio-ether (VI, R=Et; R'=CH₂CO₂Et, 9 g.) was gradually added to molecular sodium (1.8 g.) suspended in dry benzene (150 c.c.). It was

then left at the room temperature (25°) overnight. The sodium salt thus precipitated was washed with a few c.c. of benzene. This was then decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid in the cold, and was extracted with further quantity of benzene, dried, and benzene distilled away. The residual oil, thus left, was distilled, b.p. 140°/5 mm. This on keeping solidified to greenish needles, m.p. 54°. (Found: S, 15.6. $C_{10}H_{12}(O)_2S$ requires S, 15.1 per cent). This gives an indophenin reaction with isatin in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid and gives a phenolic colour with ferric chloride (VIII).

3-Oxy-7-carbethoxy-4:6-dihydrothionaphthene (Va).—To a suspension of emulsified sodium (1.2 g.) in sodium-dried benzene (50 c.c.) cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (15 g.) was slowly added in the cold. After the completion of the reaction, it was left at room temperature (25°) for 8 hours. Ethyl monochloroacetate (8 g.) was then added and the mixture was refluxed (16 hours). On cooling it was then treated with excess of water containing a few c.c. of hydrochloric acid and was extracted with further quantity of benzene, the benzene dried, and removed. The residual oil was distilled at 150°-52°/4.5 mm., which solidified on keeping to thick elongated plates, m.p. 59°. (Found: S, 14.1. $C_{11}H_{14}(O)_2S$ requires S, 14.2 per cent).

Condensation of Aldehydes with Thio-acids or Thio-esters, (VI & VII, R=H; R'=H or Et).—The thio-acids or thio-esters were dissolved in alcohol (5 c.c.) saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0° and mixed with aldehydes in equimolecular proportions, and allowed to stand over ice (1 hour). The solid separating was collected, washed with ice-water and crystallised from acetic acid or alcohol. The following compounds were prepared from thio-acids (VI, R=R'=H):—

*Di-(1-carboxy- Δ^1 -thiocyclopentenyl)-p-methoxyphenylmethane (IVa, R=H; R'=C₆H₄(OMe), m.p. 185° (decomp.), from thio-acid (1 g.), and anisaldehyde (1 g.). (Found: S, 15.3. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4S_2$ requires S, 15.7 per cent). *Di-(1-carboxy- Δ^1 -thiocyclopentenyl)-phenylmethane (IVa, R=H; R'=Ph), m.p. 221° (decomp.), from thio-acid (1 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 g.). (Found: S, 17.1. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4S_2$ requires S, 17.0 per cent). *Di-(1-carboxy- Δ^1 -thiocyclopentenyl) cinnamylidinemethane, (IVa, R=H; R'=CH=CHPh), m.p. 127° from thio-acid (1 g.) and cinnamic aldehyde (5 g.). (Found: S, 15.3. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4S_2$ requires S, 15.7 per cent).***

The following compounds were obtained from thio-ester (VI, R=H; R'=Et): *Di-(1-carbethoxy- Δ^1 -thiocyclopentenyl)-p-methoxyphenylmethane, (IVa, R=Et; R'=C₆H₄(OMe), m.p. 118°, from thio-ester (1 g.) and anisaldehyde (1 g.). (Found: C, 61.9; H, 6.6; S, 14.1. $C_{24}H_{26}O_6S_2$ requires C, 62.3; H, 6.4; S, 13.9 per cent). *Di-(1-carbethoxy- Δ^1 -thio-**

cyclopentenyl)-4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenylmethane, [IVa, R=Et; R'=C₆H₃(OH)(OMe)], m.p. 136°, from thio-ester (1.3 g.) and vanillin (1 g.). (Found: C, 59.9; H, 6.5. C₂₄H₃₀O₆S₂ requires C, 60.2; H, 6.3 per cent). Di-(1-carbethoxythiocyclopentenyl)-phenylmethane (IVa, R=Et; R'=Ph), m.p. 140°, from benzaldehyde (1 g.) and thio-ester (1 g.). (Found: C, 63.64; H, 6.4. C₂₃H₂₆O₄S₂ requires C, 63.88; H, 6.7 per cent). The molecular weight of this compound was determined by freezing point method in benzene solution. (Found: M.W., 424. C₂₃H₂₆O₄S₂ requires M.W., 430). The corresponding simple methane analogue, m.p. 117° (IVa, R=Et; R'=H), from formaldehyde (2 c.c. of 40% aq. soln.) and thio-ester (1 g.) (Found: S, 17.6. C₁₇H₂₄O₂S₂ requires S, 18.0 per cent).

The following compounds were prepared from the thio-acid (VII, R=R'=H): α -Keto- β - γ -tetramethylene- μ -phenyl-thioxine, (III, R=Ph), m.p. 85°, from benzaldehyde (1 g.) and thio-acid (1 g.) (Found: C, 67.9; H, 5.9. C₁₄H₁₄O₂S requires C, 68.2; H, 5.7 per cent). The corresponding 2-(3'-methoxy-4'-hydroxy)-phenyl analogue (III, R=H(O). C₆H₃(OMe)), m.p. 178° from vanillin (1 g.) and thio-acid (1 g.). (Found: C, 61.5; H, 5.4. C₁₃H₁₄O₄S requires C, 61.6; H, 5.5 per cent). The 2-(3'-methoxyphenyl) analogue, (III, R=C₆H₄(OMe)), m.p. 124°, from thio-acid (1 g.) and anisaldehyde (0.5 g.). (Found: C, 65.3; H, 6.0. C₁₃H₁₄O₃S requires C, 65.2; H, 5.8 per cent).

Benzaldehyde was similarly condensed with thio-ester (VII, R=Et; R'=H). The product obtained was found to be identical with the compound obtained from the thioketo-acid and benzaldehyde.

Thio-thiol Estimation.—The results of the estimation of the two tautomeric forms of the thioketo-esters are given below.

TABLE I.

$\begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2 \\ \quad \quad \\ \text{CH}_2-\text{CH} \end{array} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CS} \\ \diagdown \text{CO}_2\text{Et} \end{array}$	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{CH}_2 \quad \text{CH}_2 \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{CH}_2 \quad \text{CH} \cdot \text{C}(\text{O})_2\text{Et} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{CS} \end{array}$		
(A)	(B)		
Solvent	Temp.	A. Thiol.	B. Thiol.
EtOH	30°	36.6%	77.4%
EtOH	60°	35.1	75.7

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